

Chinese Public Companies Systematically Omitted Disclosure of Related Party Transaction with Government-related Entities

CPA Jim

I. Facts:

1. Bank of China (中国银行), China Construction Bank (中国建设银行), Industrial and Commercial Bank of China(中国工商银行), Bank of Communications Limited(交通银行) and Agricultural Bank of China(中国农业银行) claimed their financial statements for year 2019 were prepared in accordance with IFRSs.

2. China State Construction Engineering Corporation Ltd(中国建筑股份有限公司 or CSCEC) stated in its bond prospectus that by 30 September 2019, the amounts of credit facility granted by these banks to the group headed by it were RMB350 billion, RMB320 billion, RMB140 billion, RMB230 billion and RMB 300 billion respectively. Used credit facility i.e., loans were RMB95 billion, RMB200 billion, RMB80 billion, RMB70 billion and RMB 130 billion respectively (Figure 1)

截至2019年9月30日,中建股份及子企业在各银行的集团授信额度总计为2.1万亿元,已使用额度0.9万亿元,占授信总额的42.86%,主要授信情况如下表所示:

表 7-2: 发行人主要银行集团授信情况表

单位: 亿元

序号	授信银行	授信额度	已使用	未使用
1	中国建设银行	3200	2000	1200
2	中国银行	3500	950	2550
3	中国工商银行	1400	800	600
4	中国农业银行	3000	1300	1700
5	国家开发银行	1500	1200	300
6	中国进出口银行	400	90	310
7	交通银行	2300	700	1600
8	招商银行	700	220	480

(Figure 1 Credit Facility and Loans granted to 中国建筑股份有限公司)

3. CSCEC is controlled by the State Council of the People's Republic of China (PRC). In Figure 2, CSCEC confirmed it was controlled by State-owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission of the State Council.

(二) 控股股东及实际控制人情况

截至 2019 年 9 月 30 日，中建集团持有发行人的国家股 2,363,069.60 万股，占发行人股权比例的 56.29%，是发行人的控股股东。国务院国有资产管理委员会为发行人的实际控制人。

截至本募集说明书签署日，公司与实际控制人之间的产权和控制关系如下图所示：

1、 母公司情况

(a) 母公司基本情况

	注册地	业务性质
中建集团	中国北京	投资控股

本集团的最终控制方为国资委。

(b) 母公司注册资本及其变化

	2018 年 12 月 31 日	本年增加	本年减少	2019 年 12 月 31 日
中建集团	10,000,000	-	-	10,000,000

(c) 母公司对本公司的持股比例和表决权比例

	2019 年 12 月 31 日		2018 年 12 月 31 日	
	持股比例	表决权比例	持股比例	表决权比例
中建集团	<u>56.30%</u>	56.30%	56.28%	56.28%

2、 子公司情况

子公司的基本情况及相关信息见附注六。

中国建筑股份有限公司

(Figure 2 Control Structure of 中国建筑股份有限公司)

Chinese government entities are related parties to banks

4. Bank of China stated in the footnote 43.1 that it's subject to the control of the State Council of the PRC government. Bank of China only disclosed the bank entered into extensive banking transactions with government authorities, agencies, affiliates and other State controlled entities(government entities) in the normal course of business on commercial terms, including, among other things, purchase and redemption of investment securities, underwriting and distribution of Treasury bonds, foreign exchange transactions and derivative transactions, lending, provision of credit and guarantees and deposit placing and taking.¹

¹ 2019 Annual Report of Bank of China.

<https://pic.bankofchina.com/bocappd/report/202003/P020200327552610006350.pdf>

5. China Construction Bank disclosed in the footnote 60 that its parent companies are China Investment Corporation (CIC) and Central Huijin Investment Ltd. (Huijin). As at 31 December 2019, Huijin directly held 57.11% of shares of the Bank. The related companies under parent companies include the subsidiaries under parent companies and other associates and joint ventures. The Group's transactions with parent companies and their affiliates mainly include deposit taking, entrusted asset management, operating leases, lending, purchase and sale of debt securities, money market transactions and inter-bank clearing. These transactions are priced based on market prices and conducted under normal commercial terms. ²

6. As approved by the State Council, CIC was established on 29 September 2007 with a registered capital of \$200 billion raised with the proceeds of the government bond issued by the Ministry of Finance in the amount of CNY 1,550 billion. ³

7. Huijin was incorporated on 16 December 2003 as a wholly-state-owned investment company. It was registered in Beijing with registered capital of RMB828,209 million. In September 2007, the Ministry of Finance issued special treasury bonds and acquired all the shares of Huijin from the People's Bank of China. The acquired shares were injected into CIC as part of its initial capital contribution. However, Huijin's principal shareholder rights are exercised by the State Council. The members of the Board of Directors and Supervisory Committee of Huijin are appointed by, and are accountable to, the State Council. ⁴

8. By 31 December 2019, 34.71% and 31.14% shares of Industrial and Commercial Bank of China were held by Huijin and Ministry of Finance(MOF), a department under the State Council of PRC, respectively. The bank in the footnote 49 disclosed similar information Bank of China disclosed mentioned in the paragraph 4. ⁵

9. By 31 December 2019, Bank of Communications Limited issued a total of 74 billion ordinary shares, 43.4 billion or 58.49% of which were owned by State (including state-owned shares and state-owned legal person shares). The bank in

² China Construction Bank Corporation Annual Report 2019.

http://www.ccb.com/en/newinvestor/upload/20200428_1588066796/20200428214237304314.pdf

³ CIC Annual Report 2019. <http://www.china-inv.cn/chinainven/xhtml/Media/2019EN.pdf>

⁴ CSC Financial Co., Ltd. Annual Report 2019.

<https://www1.hkexnews.hk/listedco/listconews/sehk/2020/0417/2020041700312.pdf>

⁵ Industrial and Commercial Bank of China Annual Report 2019.

<http://v.icbc.com.cn/userfiles/Resources/ICBCLTD/download/2020/2019AnnualReport.pdf>

the footnote 44 disclosed similar information Bank of China disclosed mentioned in paragraph 4.⁶

10. By 31 December 2019, Agricultural Bank of China's shareholders included Huijin, owning 40% shareholding, and MOF, owning 35% shareholding. The bank in the footnote 40 disclosed similar information Bank of China disclosed mentioned in the paragraph 4.⁷

II. Requirement:

11. International Accounting Standard 24 Related Party Disclosures (IAS 24)'s paragraphs 1–29 and the Appendix have equal authority. IAS 24 is a standard of IFRSs issued by The International Accounting Standards Board. Paragraph 26 of IAS 24 required that if a reporting entity applies the exemption on government-related entities, it shall disclose the following about the transactions and related outstanding balances related to government-related entities: (a) the name of the government and the nature of its relationship with the reporting entity (ie control, joint control or significant influence);(b) the following information in sufficient detail to enable users of the entity's financial statements to understand the effect of related party transactions on its financial statements:(i)the nature and amount of each individually significant transaction; and (ii) for other transactions that are collectively, but not individually, significant, a qualitative or quantitative indication of their extent. Types of transactions include those conducted with ordinary entities as defined in paragraph 21 of IAS 24.

12. Paragraph 27 of IAS 24 required that to determine the level of detail to be disclosed in accordance with the requirements in paragraph 26(b),” the reporting entity shall consider the closeness of the related party relationship and other factors relevant in establishing the level of significance of the transaction such as whether it is: (a) significant in terms of size...”

III. Analysis:

13. Bank of China stated group's largest outstanding loans RMB69.76 billion were made to a non-related party individual borrower. The loans Bank of China

⁶ Bank of Communications Annual Report 2019.

<http://www.bankcomm.com/BankCommSite/fileDownload.do?fileId=c3ceaa86f07c460aa24b2b52e5cfc79f>

⁷ Agricultural Bank of China Annual Report 2019. <http://www.abchina.com/en/investor-relations/performance-reports/annual-reports/202004/P020200428576090111267.pdf>

made to CSCEC group but went undisclosed by Bank of China were RMB95 billion beyond its disclosed largest outstanding loans to individual borrower.

14. China Construction Bank group's loans made to top one single borrower by 31 Dec 2019 were RMB70 billion. The loans China Construction Bank made to CSCEC group but went undisclosed by China Construction Bank were RMB200 billion beyond its disclosed largest outstanding loans to individual borrower.

15. Industrial and Commercial Bank of China group's loans made to top two single borrower by 31 Dec 2019 were RMB60 billion. The loans Industrial and Commercial Bank of China made to CSCEC group but went undisclosed by Industrial and Commercial Bank of China were RMB80 billion beyond its disclosed second largest outstanding loans to individual borrower.

16. Bank of Communications Limited group's loans made to top one single borrower by 31 Dec 2019 were RMB37 billion. The loans Bank of Communications Limited made to CSCEC group but went undisclosed by Bank of Communications Limited were RMB70 billion beyond its disclosed largest outstanding loans to individual borrower.

17. Agricultural Bank of China's loans made to top one single borrower by 31 Dec 2019 were RMB117 billion. The loans Agricultural Bank of China made to CSCEC group but went undisclosed by Agricultural Bank of China were RMB130 billion beyond its disclosed largest outstanding loans to individual borrower. 75% of Agricultural Bank of China's shares were owned by agencies of State Council of PRC.

18. Chinese banks mentioned above also purchased bonds of other Chinese government entities, supplied loans to other government entities and supplied investment banking services to them. For example, China Construction Bank and Bank of China were joint underwriters of RMB10 billion Middle Term Notes

issued by China State Railway Group Company Ltd in 2019.

中国国家铁路集团有限公司
2019年度第二期中期票据募集说明书

发行人：中国国家铁路集团有限公司

发行金额：人民币壹佰亿元

期限：3年

担保情况：无担保

评级机构：联合资信评估有限公司

发行人主体长期信用等级：AAA

本期中期票据信用等级：AAA

联席主承销商：中国银行股份有限公司

联席主承销商：中国建设银行股份有限公司

2019年11月

Figure 3 Underwriters of RMB10 billion Middle Term Notes issued by China State Railway Group Company Ltd

19. These Chinese banks didn't disclose the nature and amount of each individually significant transaction with CSCEC and Chinese government entities and for other transactions that are collectively, but not individually, significant, a qualitative or quantitative indication of their extent.

20. Omitting information about such large numbers of related party transactions to disable users of the entity's financial statements to understand the effect of related party transactions on their financial statements.

21. These banks' securities are listed in Hong Kong, Tokyo and London.

21.1 China Construction Bank

Bonds

CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION, HONG KONG BRANCH

84FO CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORP., HK 1.00% SRS A NTS 04/08/23

Instruments: 4 | Amount raised: \$500,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION, HONG KONG BRANCH

84FW CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORP., HK 1.25% SRS B NTS 04/08/25

Instruments: 4 | Amount raised: \$700,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION, HONG KONG BRANCH

76LR CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORP., HK FLTG RTE NTS 22/10/22

Instruments: 4 | Amount raised: \$1,000,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION, HONG KONG BRANCH

47CT CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORP., HK FLTG RTE NTS 24/09/21

Instruments: 4 | Amount raised: \$1,000,000,000.00

Bonds

CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION, LUXEMBOURG BRANCH

66PR CHINA CONSTRUCTION BANK CORPORATION ZERO CPN SNR GRN BDS 22/04/24

Instrument: 1 | Amount raised: €800,000,000.00

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Q China Construction Bank

939	China Construction Bank Corporation - H Shares	Equities
5050	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch 3.00% N2022	Debt Securities
5112	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5173	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2021	Debt Securities
5802	China Construction Bank Corp 4.25% Tier 2 Dated Cap B2029	Debt Securities
40027	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
40332	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch 1.00% N2023	Debt Securities
40333	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch 1.25% N2025	Debt Securities
85700	China Construction Bank (Asia) Corp Ltd.3.95% CNY Notes 2021	Debt Securities
85701	China Construction Bank (Asia) Corp Ltd.4.08% CNY Notes 2024	Debt Securities

Q ccb

939	China Construction Bank Corporation - H Shares	Equities
4303	CCBL (Cayman) 1 Corporation Ltd. 3.50% Guaranteed Notes 2024	Debt Securities
4319	CCBL (Cayman) 1 Corporation Ltd. 3.875% Guaranteed Notes2029	Debt Securities
5050	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch 3.00% N2022	Debt Securities
5112	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5173	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2021	Debt Securities
5437	CCB Life Insurance Co. Ltd. 4.50% Core Tier 2 Capital Sec	Debt Securities
5802	China Construction Bank Corp 4.25% Tier 2 Dated Cap B2029	Debt Securities
40027	China Construction Bank Corporation, HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
40284	China Construction Bk Corporation Tier 2 Dated Capital B2030	Debt Securities

Jun. 27, 2019	China Construction Bank Corporation	¥20,000,000,000 0.21 per cent. Notes due 2022 by China Construction Bank Corporation, Tokyo Branch under the U.S.\$15,000,000,000 Medium Term Note Programme	00730799	XS2017329728	10667	Specified Securities Information
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21.2 Bank of China

London
Stock Exchange

Instrument

Bank o

All (17771)

Instrument (2)

Issuer (4)

2 results (2 showing)

Instrument

Bonds

BANK OF CHINA LIMITED, LONDON BRANCH

31TT BANK OF CHINA LIMITED, LONDON BRANC FLTG RTE NTS 10/08/23

Instrument: 1 | Amount raised: £300,000,000.00

Q Bank of China

3988	Bank of China Ltd. - H Shares	Equities
4440	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4441	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch 4.00% Notes 2028	Debt Securities
4460	Bank of China Ltd., Singapore Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4619	Bank of China Ltd. USD 3.60% Non-Cum Perp Offshore Pref Sh	Equities
5115	Bank of China Ltd., London Branch Floating Rate Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5236	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5369	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch 3.00% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5431	Bank of China Ltd., acting thru Sydney branch FR Notes 2022A	Debt Securities
5432	Bank of China Ltd., Macau Branch 2.875% Notes 2022B	Debt Securities

Q BOC

2388	BOC Hong Kong (Holdings) Ltd.	Equities
2588	BOC Aviation Ltd.	Equities
3329	BOCOM International Holdings Co. Ltd.	Equities
4440	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4441	Bank of China Ltd., Hong Kong Branch 4.00% Notes 2028	Debt Securities
4460	Bank of China Ltd., Singapore Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4494	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4619	Bank of China Ltd. USD 3.60% Non-Cum Perp Offshore Pref Sh	Equities
5047	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5115	Bank of China Ltd., London Branch Floating Rate Notes 2023	Debt Securities

Dec. 07, 2018	Bank of China Limited	Bank of China Limited, Tokyo Branch JPY30,000,000,000 0.42 per cent. Notes due 2021 under the U.S.\$40,000,000,000 Medium Term	00610799	XS1899011784	10547	Specified Securities Information
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21.3 Bank of Communications

Q Bank of Communications

3328	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. - H Shares	Equities
4494	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5047	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5203	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5809	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. Tier 2 Capital Bonds 2026	Debt Securities
5912	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5914	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch 2.85% Notes 2024	Debt Securities
40134	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
40135	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch 2.25% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
40314	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities

Q BOCOM

3329	BOCOM International Holdings Co. Ltd.	Equities
4494	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5047	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5203	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5533	Bocom Leasing Management Hong Kong Co. Ltd. 4.00% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5536	Bocom Leasing Management Hong Kong Co. Ltd. 4.375% Notes2024	Debt Securities
5728	Bocom Leasing Management Hong Kong Co. Ltd. 2.625% N2024 A	Debt Securities
5729	Bocom Leasing Management Hong Kong Co. Ltd. FR Notes 2024 B	Debt Securities
5809	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. Tier 2 Capital Bonds 2026	Debt Securities
5912	Bank of Communications Co., Ltd. HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities

21.4 Agricultural Bank of China

Instrument

Agricultural Bank of China

All (17768)

Instrument (1)

Issuer (2)

Pages and documents (6240)

News (11525)

1 results (1 showing)

Instrument

Bonds

AGRICULTURAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED LONDON BRANCH

B052 AGRICULTURAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED 0.80% NTS 18/05/24

Instrument: 1 | Amount raised: \$300,000,000.00

Q Agricultural Bank of China		
1288	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd. - H Shares	Equities
5025	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch FR Notes 2021	Debt Securities
5028	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch FR Notes 2023	Debt Securities
5609	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch FR Notes 2022	Debt Securities
40423	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch 1.00% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
40424	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch 1.00% Notes 2023	Debt Securities
40425	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., HK Branch 1.20% Notes 2025	Debt Securities
40537	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., NY Branch 0.85% Notes 2024	Debt Securities
40538	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., NY Branch 1.25% Green N2026	Debt Securities
40601	Agricultural Bank of China Ltd., Macao Branch 0.66% N2023	Debt Securities

21.5 Industrial and Commercial Bank of China

Issuer ▼

Industrial and Commercial Bank of China

All (19981)

Issuer (1)

Pages and documents (7087)

News (12893)

1 results (1 showing)

Issuer

Bonds

INDUSTRIAL AND COMMERCIAL BANK OF CHINA LIMITED

92MT INDUSTRIAL & COMMERCIAL BK CHINA LD FLT RTE NTS 17/10/24

Instruments: 6 | Amount raised: £500,000,000.00

Q ICBC		
1398	Industrial and Commercial Bank of China Ltd. - H Shares	Equities
3011	ICBC CICC USD Money Market ETF	ETPs
3167	ICBC CSOP S&P New China Sectors ETF	ETPs
4489	ICBCIL Finance Co. Ltd. Floating Rate Notes 2023	Debt Securities
4545	ICBCIL Finance Co. Ltd. 2.50% Notes 2021	Debt Securities
4604	ICBC EUR 6.00% Non-Cum, Non-Part, Perpetual Offshore PrefShs	Equities
4620	ICBC USD 3.58% Non-Cum Perpetual Offshore Pref Shs	Equities
5014	ICBCIL Finance Co. Ltd. 3.125% Notes 2022	Debt Securities
5015	ICBCIL Finance Co. Ltd. 3.625% Notes 2027	Debt Securities
5119	ICBC (Asia) Ltd. Floating Rate Green Bonds 2023	Debt Securities

